

Mobility vs. Contiguity: Spatially Explicit Graph Neural Networks for COVID-19 Forecasting

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Abstract. Assessing how different graph constructions affect spatio-temporal forecasting is essential for avoiding misleading predictions and ineffective interventions across domains such as epidemic control, transportation, and environmental monitoring. Graph neural networks (GNNs) offer a powerful framework for modelling these processes, but the choice of graph representation, whether based on geographic contiguity, transport networks, or mobility flows, remains underexplored. This study evaluates and compares five graph designs for forecasting daily COVID-19 infection rates per 100,000 residents in Glasgow and Edinburgh (2020–2023), including contiguity, road distance, mobility, and hybrids that integrate mobility with either contiguity or road distance. Using a 7-day sliding input window to predict the subsequent 7 days, and assessing performance via MAE, RMSE, MAPE, and R^2 , we observe city-specific heterogeneity: mobility-informed hybrids achieve the best forecasts in Glasgow but not in Edinburgh. These findings suggest that the value of mobility is context-dependent, shaped by urban form and travel intensity. More broadly, the study points to the potential importance of tailoring graph construction to local conditions, offering methodological insights for epidemic modelling and other spatio-temporal forecasting applications.

Keywords: Geospatial Artificial Intelligence · Spatially Explicit Graph Neural Networks · Mobility networks · Spatio-temporal modelling · COVID-19 Forecasting

1 Introduction

Spatially explicit graph neural networks (GNNs) can model spatially structured time series where interactions among places shape outcomes, enhancing many downstream tasks, e.g., traffic forecasting [16], epidemic spread prediction [9], and air pollution forecasting [10]. However, the choice of graph (e.g., contiguity, transportation connectivity, or measured mobility) remains under explored and may be context dependent. Spatial interactions can influence COVID-19 spread, and graph-based models provide a way to represent such dependencies. However, their advantages depend on context, data quality, and modelling assumptions.

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As such, this study forecasts daily COVID-19 infection rates and evaluates five different graph designs based on the backbone of Diffusion Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (DCRNN) [17] between two Scottish cities that differ in population distribution and travel intensity. We aim to answer two important questions: ***when** does mobility improve the prediction over, or combined with, contiguity (i.e., geographic adjacency), and **how** should graphs be combined?*

Studies have begun to explore the potential of Spatially explicit GNNs, particularly in epidemic forecasting. Kapoor et al. [15] examined spatio-temporal GNNs for COVID-19 forecasting, showing that their graph-based representations outperform purely temporal baselines. Witzke et al. [28] further demonstrated that mobility data can improve the prediction of incidence trends using graph neural networks. More recently, Duarte et al. [11] highlighted the advantages of integrating mobility flows directly into graph learning frameworks for epidemic forecasting.

Despite these advances, most research studies only focused on mobility-based graphs, and few attempt to integrate different factors [3, 8], such as geographic adjacency [12], mobility flows [7], and road networks [18]. An open question remains: *how should graphs be constructed and potentially combined?* In the domain of traffic prediction, hybrid graph designs (e.g., combining road networks with mobility demand) have been more widely explored [29, 30]. Yet, systematic comparisons of these alternatives across different urban contexts seem to be still limited. It remains unclear whether mobility-based graphs consistently offer benefits, or whether their effectiveness varies depending on city-specific characteristics such as population density or travel patterns.

To address these limitations, this study explores the comparative performance of five graph construction strategies within the DCRNN architecture: (1) geographic adjacency, (2) road network distances, (3) mobility flows, (4) hybrid graphs combining mobility with road networks, and (5) hybrid graphs combining mobility with geographic adjacency. Using daily COVID-19 infection rates per 100,000 residents at the InterZone level from 2020 to 2023 and a 7-day input window to forecast the subsequent 7 days, we conduct a comparative analysis in Glasgow and Edinburgh, two Scottish cities with contrasting demographic and mobility profiles. The study aims to examine how different graph designs may influence forecasting performance and to provide guidance on tailoring graph-based neural networks to local urban contexts in epidemic modelling

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Data Sources

This study focuses on Glasgow and Edinburgh, two major Scottish cities with contrasting demographics and mobility patterns. Daily COVID-19 infection data at the InterZone level from March 2020 to February 2023 were obtained from Public Health Scotland [21].¹ Small counts (≤ 2 cases per zone per day) were

¹ <https://www.opendata.nhs.scot/dataset/covid-19-in-scotland>

suppressed for confidentiality. To address this, we applied multiple imputation using the `mice` package in R [6]. Following standard practice in the missing data literature, we generated 20 imputed datasets. While Rubin originally suggested that as few as 3–5 imputations might be sufficient, subsequent methodological studies have shown that using a larger number (e.g., 20–40) improves the stability and precision of parameter estimates [5, 13, 25]. The 20 completed datasets were averaged to produce infection rates per 100,000 residents. Figure 1 illustrates the temporal evolution of infection rates in both cities, highlighting substantial fluctuations across pandemic waves and differences in magnitude between Glasgow and Edinburgh. These descriptive plots provide the empirical motivation for applying spatio-temporal models capable of adapting to heterogeneous dynamics.

Population mobility data were accessed from the Urban Big Data Centre (UBDC) [26].² These origin–destination matrices provide anonymised flows between InterZones, expressed as percentages of resident movements. Road and rail network data were downloaded from the Geofabrik OpenStreetMap server for Scotland [20] and processed with the `dodgr` package to compute shortest-path distances for multiple transport modes. Together, these datasets enabled the construction of diverse graph structures that capture both geographic adjacency and mobility interactions.

Fig. 1: Weekly average 7days COVID-19 rate per 100,000 population in Glasgow and Edinburgh (2020–2023).

2.2 Graph Construction

Five graph structures were designed to represent spatial and mobility relationships.

- (1) **Geographic adjacency:**

$$w_{ij}^{\text{geo}} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if zones } i \text{ and } j \text{ share a common boundary,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

² <https://data.ubdc.ac.uk/datasets/6d87635c-96bb-4b7a-9a2e-676bb250032d>

(2) **Road network:**

$$w_{ij}^{\text{road}} = \frac{1}{d_{ij}^{\text{road}} + \epsilon}, \quad i \neq j, \quad (2)$$

where d_{ij}^{road} denotes the shortest-path distance between zones i and j through the multimodal road and rail network, and ϵ is a small smoothing constant to avoid division by zero.

Fig. 2: Step-by-step workflow of the study: data collection, preprocessing, graph construction, modelling, and evaluation.

(3) Mobility flows:

$$w_{ij}^{\text{mob}} = \frac{1}{2}(f_{ij} + f_{ji}), \quad i \neq j, \quad (3)$$

where f_{ij} is the proportion of trips from zone i to zone j . The matrix is symmetrized to obtain an undirected representation, where edge weights reflect the average of flows in both directions. Although OD matrices are inherently directional, we adopt a symmetric representation for two reasons. First, transmission risk is bidirectional, since movements in both directions can facilitate cross-zone exposure. Similar symmetric assumptions are common in epidemic modelling to simplify transmission structures [3, 23]. Second, OD data at the InterZone scale often contain sampling noise and directional imbalances; averaging f_{ij} and f_{ji} produces a more stable connectivity structure, which improves robustness when training graph neural networks.

(4) Mobility + Road:

$$W^{MR} = \alpha W^{\text{mob}} + (1 - \alpha)W^{\text{road}}, \quad (4)$$

(5) Mobility + Geographic adjacency:

$$W^{MG} = \alpha W^{\text{mob}} + (1 - \alpha)W^{\text{geo}}, \quad (5)$$

which combines dynamic mobility flows with static geographic adjacency.

Each matrix $W = [w_{ij}]$ specifies the weighted adjacency structure used in the DCRNN model, where higher values of w_{ij} represent stronger spatial proximity or greater mobility flow intensity between zones.

The coefficient α ranged from 0.5 to 0.9, ensuring that mobility contributed at least equally to the hybrid structures. This range reflects the assumption that mobility is a dominant driver of transmission while allowing sensitivity to spatial constraints. Figure 3 presents visualisations of the graph structures, offering an intuitive illustration of the differences between geographic adjacency, road connectivity, and mobility flows.

2.3 Model and Training

The DCRNN architecture was employed, integrating diffusion convolution with recurrent units to capture temporal dynamics alongside spatial diffusion over graphs. Forecasting was formulated as a multistep task in which a 7-day sliding input window was used to predict the subsequent 7 days at the InterZone level. The window advanced by one day at each step, generating overlapping input-output sequences across the entire time series. This rolling-window design functions as a time-series analogue to cross-validation, maximising data utilisation while preserving temporal ordering.

To ensure comparability between Glasgow and Edinburgh, all model and training hyperparameters were kept identical across cities, including the number of recurrent layers (3), hidden units per layer (128), the maximum diffusion step

(a) Geographic adjacency.

(b) Road network.

(c) Mobility flows.

Fig. 3: Visualisations of the graph structures.

(3), the sequence length and forecast horizon (both set to 7), the use of dual random-walk filters, and curriculum learning with a decay of 300 steps. Training hyperparameters such as the learning rate (0.001 with multi-step decay), batch size (32), dropout (0.1), gradient clipping (5), and early-stopping patience (30) were also fixed. Keeping these hyperparameters constant prevents differences in model capacity or optimisation behaviour from influencing performance, allowing the analysis to isolate the impact of graph construction strategies.

Data were split chronologically into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%). The split points were selected not only by proportion but also with reference to fluctuations in weekly infection rates, ensuring that each subset contained representative epidemic dynamics. Later stages of the pandemic were reserved for out-of-sample evaluation.

All infection rates were standardised using Z-score normalisation, defined as

$$x' = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}, \quad (6)$$

where x is the raw infection rate, μ the mean, and σ the standard deviation. The inverse transformation was applied before computing the evaluation metrics to retain interpretability in the original units.

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

Performance was assessed using four standard error metrics widely applied in forecasting studies [14, 19]: mean absolute error (MAE), root mean squared error (RMSE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2).

Since MAPE is undefined when $y_i = 0$ and unstable for small denominators, we adopt a modified version MAPE_ε by adding a small constant $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$ to the denominator. This ensures numerical stability for small-area incidence rates while retaining the interpretability of percentage error. The metrics are defined as:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{MAPE}_\varepsilon = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i + \varepsilon} \right| \right) \times 100\%, \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}. \quad (10)$$

3 Results

3.1 Glasgow

Table 1 shows that hybrid graphs integrating mobility flows with geographic adjacency clearly outperform the single source alternatives in Glasgow. The best performing specification assigns 60% weight to mobility and 40% to geographic adjacency, achieving MAE = 80.01, RMSE = 133.22, MAPE = 48.89%, and $R^2 = 0.90$. Compared with the pure contiguity graph, this corresponds to a reduction of 1.6% in MAE, 14.83% in RMSE, and 4.97% in MAPE, highlighting the value of incorporating mobility information. The second and third ranked configurations (90% and 50% mobility weights, respectively) yield similarly competitive results, with RMSE values around 135–138.

To visualise the multi-metric performance differences more clearly, Figure 4 presents a radar chart that summarises all four normalised metrics (MAE, RMSE, MAPE, and R^2). The hybrid mobility–adjacency graphs form the largest enclosed area in the radar plot, indicating consistently strong performance across all evaluation metrics. In contrast, single-source graphs (contiguity, road distance, or mobility alone) show more uneven profiles, performing well on some metrics but worse on others. This graphical summary reinforces the tabulated results, showing visually that mobility-enhanced hybrid graphs provide the most balanced and accurate forecasts in Glasgow.

Table 1: Forecasting performance of different graph structures in Glasgow.

Models	MAE (/100k)	RMSE (/100k)	MAPE (%)	R^2
Geographic adjacency	81.61	148.05	43.92%	0.88
Road	85.89	155.46	47.50%	0.87
Mobility	81.47	141.32	47.62%	0.89
Mobility + Road				
50% + 50%	82.62	144.64	48.88%	0.89
60% + 40%	84.20	150.78	46.47%	0.88
70% + 30%	83.15	147.41	46.88%	0.88
80% + 20%	84.09	153.50	46.33%	0.87
90% + 10%	83.91	147.55	48.84%	0.88
Mobility + Geographic adjacency				
50% + 50% ⁽³⁾	82.32	137.81	48.43%	0.90
60% + 40% ⁽¹⁾	80.01	133.22	48.89%	0.90
70% + 30%	80.65	135.89	50.27%	0.90
80% + 20%	82.38	136.45	52.55%	0.90
90% + 10% ⁽²⁾	80.33	135.45	47.55%	0.90

Note: Superscripts ⁽¹⁾, ⁽²⁾, and ⁽³⁾ denote the top three models ranked by overall performance across MAE, RMSE, MAPE, and R^2 . MAE and RMSE are reported in units of the infection rate, defined as daily COVID-19 cases per 100,000 population (/100k).

The training and validation loss curves in Figure 5(a–c) confirm that the three top hybrid models converge smoothly, with validation loss stabilising at a

Fig. 4: Radar chart comparing the forecasting performance of all graph designs in Glasgow. For MAE, RMSE, MAPE: score = $1 - \frac{x - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}$. For R^2 : score = $\frac{x - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}$.

similar level across runs. These patterns indicate that incorporating mobility into spatial graphs enhances the model’s ability to capture cross-zone transmission pathways in Glasgow.

3.2 Edinburgh

In contrast, Table 2 and Figure 6 highlight a different ranking of graph structures in Edinburgh. The best performance is achieved by the geographic adjacency graph, with MAE = 78.24, RMSE=146.92, MAPE = 43.81%, and $R^2 = 0.88$. The second best configuration is the mobility graph, followed by the hybrid of 60% mobility and 40% adjacency. This ordering suggests that local contiguity relationships are more predictive of infection patterns in Edinburgh than mobility-enhanced graphs, which contrasts with the findings for Glasgow. Figure 5(d–f) shows that the top three models in Edinburgh also exhibit stable convergence, though validation loss remains slightly higher than in Glasgow, consistent with the overall larger errors reported in the metrics.

A key observation is the heterogeneity in the role of mobility across cities. In Glasgow, mobility-informed hybrid graphs deliver clear improvements over spatial or road-based structures, whereas in Edinburgh, simple geographic adjacency provides the best forecasts. These findings imply that the utility of mobility-enhanced graphs is context dependent, shaped by city-specific factors such as travel intensity, population distribution, and administrative zoning. They also underscore the importance of tailoring graph construction strategies to local conditions rather than assuming universal superiority of mobility-based representations.

Fig. 5: Training and validation loss curves for the top three models in Glasgow (a–c) and Edinburgh (d–f).

Table 2: Forecasting performance of different graph structures in Edinburgh.

Models	MAE (/100k)	RMSE (/100k)	MAPE (%)	R^2
Geographic adjacency⁽¹⁾	78.24	146.92	43.81%	0.88
Road	83.01	156.19	44.91%	0.86
Mobility⁽²⁾	79.74	148.76	43.00%	0.88
Mobility + Road				
50% + 50%	83.61	157.69	43.99%	0.86
60% + 40%	81.87	150.57	43.23%	0.87
70% + 30%	82.89	152.49	46.02%	0.87
80% + 20%	81.88	151.81	42.97%	0.87
90% + 10%	82.28	150.18	46.56%	0.87
Mobility + Geographic adjacency				
50% + 50%	83.62	157.76	44.98%	0.86
60% + 40%⁽³⁾	81.01	152.70	42.20%	0.87
70% + 30%	82.47	153.70	43.95%	0.87
80% + 20%	83.91	159.23	44.84%	0.86
90% + 10%	82.93	158.78	40.57%	0.86

Note: Superscripts ⁽¹⁾, ⁽²⁾, and ⁽³⁾ denote the top three models ranked by overall performance across MAE, RMSE, MAPE, and R^2 . MAE and RMSE are reported in units of the infection rate, defined as daily COVID-19 cases per 100,000 population (/100k)

Fig. 6: Radar chart comparing the forecasting performance of all graph designs in Edinburgh. For MAE, RMSE, MAPE: score = $1 - \frac{x - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}$. For R^2 : score = $\frac{x - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}$.

4 Discussion

An important insight from our results is that mobility information contributes most when cross zone flows are strong and heterogeneous, whereas geographic contiguity alone can suffice when transmission is predominantly local. Based on this observation, a practical procedure is to begin with contiguity, incorporate directed origin destination flows when mobility intensity is high, validate graph construction using temporally blocked cross validation, and, where possible, exploit time varying mobility data.

The comparative analysis of five graph construction strategies within the DCRNN framework reveals important differences between Glasgow and Edinburgh, highlighting the heterogeneous role of mobility in epidemic forecasting. In Glasgow, the strongest performance was obtained from a hybrid graph combining 60% mobility flows with 40% geographic adjacency. This indicates that infection spread in Glasgow is closely linked to cross zone mobility, where commuting and travel intensity act as major drivers of diffusion. In contrast, in Edinburgh, purely geographic adjacency yielded the most accurate forecasts, followed by mobility and the 60% mobility with 40% adjacency hybrid graph. This suggests that Edinburgh’s infection dynamics are more localized, with transmission patterns better explained by neighbourhood contiguity than by mobility interactions.

Figure 3 reinforces these findings. In Glasgow, mobility flows exhibit a hub and spoke configuration, with a small number of strong connections linking the central business district to peripheral zones. Such heterogeneity provides predictive information not captured by static adjacency, thereby explaining the

superior performance of mobility informed and hybrid graphs. By contrast, Edinburgh’s mobility flows in Figure 3 appear weaker and more evenly distributed, with no dominant inter zone corridors. The absence of pronounced commuting heterogeneity reduces the incremental value of mobility, making contiguity based graphs more effective in this setting. This pattern is consistent with Edinburgh’s more compact urban form and relatively homogeneous administrative zones, where shorter travel distances and a reliance on bus based commuting generate more balanced inter zone flows. Planning frameworks such as the “20-Minute Neighbourhood” strategy further reinforce this localisation by promoting evenly distributed accessibility across districts [24]. As a result, static adjacency captures the primary transmission pathways, and the added benefit of mobility information is limited in comparison to Glasgow. These contrasting outcomes demonstrate that mobility does not universally improve prediction accuracy; rather, its predictive utility depends on the demographic, geographic, and behavioural characteristics of the city. Banerjee et al. [2] similarly showed that mobility informed spatio temporal transformers (STSGT) enhance epidemic forecasting in contexts where inter regional flows are strong. Zheng et al. [31] highlighted that heterogeneity between locations can alter the role of mobility, with their HeatGNN framework explicitly modelling such differences. More broadly, the divergent results may reflect underlying urban form: Glasgow exhibits a more monocentric structure with concentrated commuting corridors, whereas Edinburgh is more compact and polycentric, with flows distributed more evenly across multiple centres. Such variation in spatial organisation shapes the heterogeneity of mobility flows and hence their predictive value, consistent with insights from urban economics and urban science [1, 4, 27].

Methodologically, the findings yield several implications. First, they challenge the common assumption that the inclusion of mobility information invariably improves forecasting accuracy. Instead, the predictive value of mobility-enhanced graphs appears to be contingent upon city-specific characteristics. Second, the results suggest that hybrid graph constructions, which integrate both dynamic mobility flows and static geographic adjacency, are particularly effective in urban contexts characterised by high levels of commuting and cross-zone interaction, as observed in Glasgow. Conversely, in settings such as Edinburgh, where infection dynamics appear more spatially localised, the benefits of hybridisation are attenuated and purely geographic structures prove sufficient. Third, the analysis highlights that the design of graph representations should not be guided by universal prescriptions, but rather by the demographic, geographic, and behavioural attributes of the study area.

5 Future Work

This study has also reflected several promising directions for further research. First, our analysis was limited to two Scottish cities, and thus extending our approaches to more cities with different scales, population density, spatial complexity, and transport connectivity would help verify whether the observed find-

ings hold universally. Second, future work should consider using higher spatio-temporal resolutions for the dynamic mobility data (e.g., mobile phone data and public transport flows), to capture fluctuations in travel behaviour (e.g., daily, weekly, and seasonal) that aggregated data may miss. Third, exploring alternative architectures beyond DCRNN would be valuable. For example, transformer-based graph models (e.g., [2]) have demonstrated strong performance in capturing spatio-temporal heterogeneity. Meanwhile, mechanistic heterogeneity models (e.g., [31]) offer promising directions to incorporate epidemiological theory into data-driven graph learning. Fourth, multi-scale spatio-temporal graph structures (e.g., [22]) can help capture patterns at different spatial granularities. Fifth, evaluating public health relevant performance metrics (e.g., early detection of surges, spatial cluster detection, and forecasting under intervention changes) would make model outputs more actionable. Sixth, incorporating time varying mobility graphs, rather than static or temporally aggregated flows, could improve sensitivity to behavioural responses and policy interventions. Such dynamic graphs would allow models to capture how mobility reductions during lockdowns or rebounds after restrictions directly reshape transmission pathways, thereby enhancing forecasting robustness.

Beyond these modelling extensions, several methodological improvements will be incorporated in future research. In particular, upcoming work will introduce broader baseline comparisons, enhanced uncertainty estimation, and more robust temporal evaluation designs to provide a fuller empirical characterisation of forecasting performance. The construction of mobility graphs will also be expanded to include directed and temporally resolved mobility flows, allowing the models to capture finer-grained behavioural and policy-driven dynamics.

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